

Persistent identifiers adoption and awareness: Survey report

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7th October 2020

Persistent identifiers adoption and awareness survey report

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Submitted to Jisc on October 7th 2020.

Introduction

Throughout 2020, Jisc has been running a project to develop and refine a national strategy and roadmap for persistent identifiers (PIDs) to enhance access to UK research. As part of this project, the team released an online survey to investigate current levels of PID awareness, adoption and integration in key systems for open research.

Understanding the baseline for PID adoption and awareness will be essential for targeting project interventions and subsequent activities, and for evaluating their impact.

The project is based on a series of specific ‘priority’ PIDs for open research. These are PIDs for grants (Digital Object Identifiers provided by Crossref), organisations (Research Organisation Registry identifiers), outputs (Digital Object Identifiers provided by Crossref and DataCite), people (Open Researcher and Contributor Identifiers), and projects (Research Activity Identifiers, provided by the Australian Research Data Commons).

These identifiers are at very different stages of development and maturity, and the project team anticipated significant variations in levels of awareness and adoption. For more mature PID systems, the survey has offered feedback on both user satisfaction and potential areas for development. For newer systems, the survey offers more insight into key areas in which respondents would like to explore their offerings.

The survey was launched at a webinar in late June 2020, and closed on August 21st 2020. It was promoted via blog posts and social media internationally, and via Jisc member communications in the UK.

The findings will inform the development of further analyses of particular PID integrations in workflows and systems which will support increased openness for UK research, and improve the efficiency and usability of existing open research workflows.

Executive summary

The survey gathered 93 responses, 75% of which were from organisations which primarily serve a UK audience. Researchers were overwhelmingly the focus of organisations responding. Funders and scholarly societies were under-represented in the sample.

The findings support the project focus on five 'priority PIDs' for open research, with DOIs for outputs and ORCID IDs for people being both widely known and adopted. Reported satisfaction with these PIDs was also high. There is widespread frustration with the lack of adoption of grant, organisation, and project PIDs. It is worth noting that ROR IDs for organisations are already the most used, despite ROR itself launching as a 'minimum viable product' in January 2019.

Issues that are hampering PID adoption are that the technical burden and costs of integration are too high, and the perceived value of PIDs is too low. The project should explore ways that technical costs or difficulty can be reduced, and should work with PID providers to articulate the value proposition of the priority PIDs (and PIDs in general) and provide evidence of the benefits of PID adoption. Membership costs are also an issue for many, especially smaller, organisations.

Key recommendations based on the survey findings are:

- Interventions are needed to improve the scale and depth of PID integration in every day workflows.
- Respondents want to see PIDs being used optimally in funding systems (both for grant application/award and for reporting), content platforms which host research outputs (including data and e-books as well as articles), and research information management tools within institutions.
- Metadata associated with PIDs is vital. It needs to be predictably present, contain more consistent elements, and be reliably maintained and updated.
- For new or emerging PIDs, there are lessons to be learned from ROR's engagement strategies, which have enabled it to make remarkable progress.
- Barriers to adoption need to be lowered.

PIDs are desired across the sector for their potential to enable better interoperability and data re-use for reporting and analysis. If the appetite for interoperable PIDs, streamlined workflows, and efficiency gains is to be met, PIDs need to be a predictable, reliable presence in key information systems across the board, and to provide access to consistent, accurate metadata.

Responses:

The survey received 93 responses.

A large majority of respondents (71%, n=67) work in a university or research institute. Multiple options could be selected, and 10 of the 20 respondents (21%) who work in a library also selected "university/research institute". Service providers/infrastructure were also fairly well represented (15%, n=14), while other types of organisation were all selected by fewer than 10% of respondents. It is unfortunate that funders and scholarly societies were not better represented in the sample. Specific outreach to these groups may be advisable to ensure balance in the wider project.

The three respondents who selected the “Other” option were from a digital repository, a national library, and the US Department of Energy Office of Science.

Which of the following best describes your organisation?

Figure 1: organisation types represented by survey respondents

Three quarters of respondents were based in the UK or worked for organisations which serve a UK-focused community.

Of the remaining respondents, some were from organisations which are based in the UK, but serve an international audience such as publishers who receive manuscripts from around the world, or system providers who have a global customer base. Others were based in countries other than the UK, but served a similarly global audience (total n=11).

Two respondents were from European organisations, two were from Australia, and single responses were also received from France, Germany, the Republic of Ireland, and the United States.

Is your organisation primarily UK-focused?

Figure 2: Geographical focus of respondents' organisations

Well over half of the respondents work for organisations that serve students (all levels), researchers, teaching and administrative staff, and librarians. Researchers (97%, n=91) and postgraduate students (94%, n=88) were the most common populations served. Nearly a quarter of respondents (23%, n=22) serve third sector groups. Other groups served were:

- Editors and publishers
- Business
- Community remit
- Local community
- Funders, publishers, governmental bodies, and other policy makers
- Commercial and third sector
- Commercial users
- Unaffiliated local researchers
- Publishers, libraries, and consortia
- General public

Which of the following groups does your organisation serve?

Figure 3: Groups served by respondents' organisations

A wide range of organisational systems were represented, with repositories (87%, n=82), research data management systems (72%, n=68), and CRIS/research management systems (61%, n=57) especially likely to be used by respondents' organisations, followed by funding (56%, n=53), HR (46%, n=43), and publishing (39%, n=37). As well as abstracting and indexing organisations (25%, n=24), a number of other organisation types were represented, including library management systems, network and identity services, access management systems, and research software management systems.

What are the key research information creation/ curation/ publication/ management systems in your organisation (check all)

Figure 4: Research information systems in use by respondents

PID awareness:

Respondents had a very high level of awareness of DOIs (98% were familiar or very familiar, n=92) and ORCID iDs (96%, n=90), both of which are being widely used in the UK and elsewhere. Somewhat more surprisingly, over half of respondents (55%, n=52) were at least somewhat familiar with ROR identifiers, despite the fact that the ROR registry launched less than two years ago. Only slightly more respondents (62%, n=58) were aware of ISNI identifiers for organisations, despite the fact that these have been around since 2012.¹ Less surprisingly, RAiDs (which were also launched in 2019) were the least well known of our priority PIDs, with just 30% of respondents (n=28) being at least somewhat familiar with them.

How familiar are you with the following PIDs? (1 = completely unaware, 5 = very familiar)

Figure 5: Reported levels of familiarity with the priority PID candidates

For the purposes of comparison, the averages of the awareness ratings is helpful. While ROR and ISNI are very close, RAiD is surprisingly well known for such a relative newcomer, especially given its very low levels of adoption outside Australia. It is likely that this is skewed somewhat by its inclusion in this project, as it has been promoted alongside the other, better established, PIDs and would therefore have been drawn to the attention of a similar audience to this survey.

¹ NB: While the project was concerned with both ROR and ISNI PIDs for organisations at the outset, the scope was narrowed to ROR IDs in response to recommendations from the focus groups which were conducted after the survey was designed.

Average awareness levels for each PID (1= completely unaware, 5= very familiar)

Figure 6: Average reported awareness rating for priority PIDs

PID adoption

Encouragingly, there is already widespread and growing adoption of the five priority PIDs that have been identified. DOIs (used — or planned to be used — by 94% of respondents' organisations, n=88) and ORCID iDs (90%, n=85) are by far the most widely adopted identifiers. Interestingly, ROR is already the most used PID for organisations (22%, n=21), compared with ISNI identifiers (20%, n=19), although there's still a long way to go. RAiDs are the least adopted of the five (3%, n=3).

Which of the following PIDs are you currently using/ planning to use at your organisation?

Figure 7: PIDs either in current or planned use at respondents' organisations

The long tail of 19 PIDs and other non-persistent identifiers that respondents report are being used in their organisations include:

- Miscellaneous local database identifiers (n=3)
- Proprietary database identifiers, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or SSRN IDs
- Commonly accepted 'Persistent' identifiers, such as ISSN, Handle, IGSN
- National identifiers, such as UKPRN, IdHAL
- Others including PubMed, SHA-1, URNs

Satisfaction with PIDs

Of the two most widely adopted PIDs, the vast majority (90%, n=85) of respondents are satisfied or completely satisfied with DOIs, while somewhat fewer — 72%, n= 64 — are satisfied or completely satisfied with ORCID iDs. Satisfaction levels with organisation identifiers are moderate. 67% of respondents were at least somewhat satisfied with ROR identifiers, and 70% at least somewhat satisfied with ISNI identifiers. RAiDs had the lowest satisfaction levels, however, there were only three reported users of these identifiers in the survey so higher levels of satisfaction would have been unexpected.

Satisfaction with PIDs

Figure 8: Reported levels of satisfaction with the priority PIDs

The benefits of PIDs

A clear majority of respondents see, or expect to see in future, a number of benefits from the adoption of PIDs. All benefits listed in the survey were ranked 4 or 5 by well over half of respondents, on a scale where 1 = low potential and 5 = high potential. Almost all respondents (91.5%, n=86) see interoperability between external systems as a high potential benefit, and large majorities are enthusiastic about the benefits from improved reporting (81.9%, n=77) and interoperability with internal systems (79.8%, n=75). Cost savings in terms of money (22.3%, n=21) was the only benefit not considered to have high potential by respondents. Conversely, nearly three times as many people (65.9%, n=62) believed that

there was high potential for cost savings in terms of time, which at some level must equate to money.

Figure 9: Perceived current or future benefits of PIDs

Barriers to PID adoption:

Respondents were also asked about potential barriers to PID adoption in their organisation. Interestingly, lack of a clear value proposition, which is often cited as a concern, was by far the least likely to be seen as a barrier, with just 24.5% of respondents (n=23) ranking it 4 or 5 on a scale where 1 = low barrier to adoption and 5 = high. In fact, the only option seen as a significant barrier by more than half of respondents was the cost of implementation (57.4%, n=54, ranked this 4 or 5). The other options were all viewed pretty similarly — cost of membership (41.5%, n=39), lack of senior leadership buy-in (42.5%, n=40), and lack of user buy-in (44.7%, n=42). The latter two are somewhat surprising given respondents' lack of concern about the value proposition.

Figure 10: Current or future barriers to PID adoption

One area that PIDs should be used in

In response to a free text question about which one area or system respondents would most like to see PIDs used in, and why, there was a clear divide between those who wanted PIDs for particular entities and those who wanted them to be better deployed in specific systems or contexts. This split has lowered the absolute number of responses in each category, and it might have been better to explore these topics as separate, explicit questions. That said, there were clear areas of consensus within the results.

Entities

People:

ORCID IDs were mentioned by 14 respondents, with most responses focused on a need for better/more consistent use of IDs and better/more metadata associated with IDs. There was a clear appetite for more mandates for ORCID use.

Outputs:

Publications were mentioned by 11 respondents in reference to various kinds of publications (such as articles or books). Shortcomings in publication PID adoption and coverage were noted, including the fact that some journals do not yet register DOIs for articles, as well as the lack of DOIs for e-books.

Data was identified as another high priority, mentioned by eight respondents. Better adoption of PIDs for research datasets is a need in its own right, but respondents also noted that better connections to corresponding publications, researchers, and funding are needed. PIDs for datasets earlier in the research cycle were also seen as desirable.

Several respondents noted that maintenance of and updates for DOI metadata can be a real issue.

Grants:

Ten respondents mentioned the need for grant identifiers. Several observed that without PIDs integrated in funding and grant metadata from the beginning, making use of that data and linking it to downstream activities and outputs was difficult, and made harder by the fact that the issue became apparent much later in the research lifecycle than the optimal stage to fix it. One respondent remarked that 'grants metadata is a real mess'.

Organisations:

While adoption was a primary concern for the six respondents who discussed organisation PIDs, curation issues for organisation metadata were also mentioned. These include coverage for sub-organisations, or cross-organisational collaborations, as well as the need to improve integration between PIDs commonly used in the research space (or specifically for research-focused organisations) and their non-academic partners, such as businesses or charities.

Projects:

Projects were mentioned by six respondents as a challenge, in particular in terms of representing them within local systems, such as CRIS, and across platforms or contexts. The need to make better links between projects, outputs, and funding was also mentioned.

Other entities mentioned included conferences, protocols, and instruments (for each, n=1).

Systems

CRIS:

Nine respondents would most like to see PIDs being used better in CRIS or other research information management systems. The perceived value of improved PID integrations included reducing duplication of effort, automating workflows, and creating better links between entities within the system itself in order to further research integrity and help identify research misconduct, such as fraudulent publication.

CRISs were described by one respondent as “the foundation of our management reporting and where we can more easily demonstrate value”. Another noted that in the absence of a CRIS, they weren’t “currently getting the full benefit of PIDs”.

Publication platforms:

Respondents grouped manuscript tracking systems and content platforms together in this category, but at the core was a need to ingest PIDs and metadata simply, and to maintain the links and relationships created through to publication “to enable the benefits of linking together research outputs for discovery and evaluation to be fully realised”.

Repositories:

The inconsistency of PID adoption in repository systems and workflows was the main issue raised by respondents, whether for data- or publication-focused repositories.

Funding systems:

Respondents noted that grant application and management systems need to use and produce PIDs throughout their processes, and to share PIDs, relationships, and metadata openly and reliably for downstream re-use.

Conclusions

The survey reveals that while there is a very long tail of PIDs or identifier-like systems in use, a significant majority of PID users are focused on what could be termed 'general' PIDs for common entities. These are used across disciplines, and across regions. These PIDs echoed the priorities which have shaped the project: grants, organisations, outputs, people and projects.

For those PIDs with the greatest current levels of adoption (DOIs, ORCID IDs) there is a desire for more effective and consistent usage. For those with lower levels of usage, respondents echoed the priorities of the project: grants, organisations and projects were repeatedly cited as a critical need.

The survey responses indicate areas of focus for the project moving forward. These include:

Improving the scale and depth of PID integration in every day workflows. The lack of consistency in PID adoption has a knock-on effect on adoption and re-use. If one cannot rely on a PID being present in a useful form, one does not build systems to take advantage of that PID.

Respondents want to see PIDs being used optimally in funding systems (both for grant application/award and for reporting), content platforms which host research outputs (including data and e-books as well as articles), and research information management tools within institutions.

Metadata associated with PIDs is vital. It needs to be predictably present, contain more consistent elements, and be reliably maintained and updated. Respondents report spending a great deal of time correcting and extending metadata. Such corrections are often then not available for subsequent re-use.

ROR has made remarkable progress in terms of both adoption and awareness in a relatively short space of time, drawing close to or overtaking incumbent organisation identifiers in the space. For new or emerging PIDs, there are lessons to be learned from ROR's engagement strategies.

Barriers to adoption need to be lowered. The technical burden and costs of integration are too high, and the perceived value of PIDs is too low. The project should explore ways that technical costs or difficulty can be reduced, and should work with PID providers to articulate the value proposition of the priority PIDs (and PIDs in general) and provide evidence of the benefits of PID adoption. Membership costs are also an issue for many, especially smaller, organisations.

PIDs are desired for their potential to enable better interoperability and data re-use for reporting and analysis. If the appetite for interoperable PIDs, streamlined workflows, and efficiency gains is to be met, PIDs need to be a predictable, reliable presence in key information systems across the board, and to provide access to consistent, accurate metadata.